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Semiotic Analysis in *The Da Vinci Code* and *Angels and Demons*' Novels by Dan Brown

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Abstract:

Semiotic is broadly used as an interdisciplinary study that all manners of communication include on it. Semiotic studies are individually attractive to whoever is fascinated in signs at large and the meaning it interpret by the signs. It is very exiting science that allows a semiotician the liberty to consider anything or any feelings as a sign and construe it to convey an idea. When the semiotic theories are applied to literature it helps a reader to understand the text, the writer, the socio- cultural background, characterization and many more divers interpretations. Literary semiotics has been a field of research constructed more aspects of the Linguistics. Semiotics is the study of signs; it is also described the signs, symbols and icons. It is study of sign and sign using behavior. It demarcated by one its founders, the Swiss linguist Ferdinand de Saussure. Semiotics is one of the finest analyses of the literary work. *The Da Vinci Code*, this is the wonderful novel with the pack of several signs, symbols which promotes to the readers to decode it and semiotic study made it easy. *Angels & Demons*' is a bestselling mystery-thriller novel both novels written by American author Dan Brown and published by Pocket Books.

Keywords: Semiotic analysis, sign, symbol, Ferdinand de Saussure, *The Da Vinci Code*, *Angels & Demons*'.

Introduction

There are several writers of mystery novels in old and early days that got incredible popularity for their writing. They used some signs and symbols and this semiotic analysis made them to solve the mystery. Semiotics does a vital role in the field of mystery fiction because it is cultural representation of language to warming signs, brands and emojis. In early days mystery writers used some traditional or historical signs which was well-known and through that investigator find the clue of the mystery. The American philosopher C. S. Peirce made useful division between three types of signs: the 'iconic' where the sign *resembles* its referent, second is the 'indexical' where sign is *associated*, possibly causally, and the 'symbolic' where sign has an *arbitrary* relation to its referent. In mystery stories sign and its meaning which woven in puzzle and investigator find the hidden truth. Here semiotic analysis of the signs plays the major role in mystery writings. Semiotics was the categorization of Signs into three parts in that the first part 'an icon' which reflects its referent. The second is 'an index' and third is 'a symbol'. Language is a sign system and it reflects the meaning through the signs. This paper focuses on the historical background of semiotics and attempts to draw attention to it as a universal genre.

What Semiotics Does

1. Identification of signs
2. Meaning of signifier
3. Signified a Personal Interpretation

There are three types of Signified-

Icons: A physical resemblance to the object like Map, Sound and Pictures.

Symbols: No physical resemblance but some signs in code.

Index: Exists because of existence of signifier for example Smoke-free.

1.1.2. Model of Semiotic Theory

Meaning is the relationship between the recipient of a sign and their personal experience or the meaning is created when the recipient makes sense of the sign by connecting and interacting with their surrounding reality. Semiotic study provides a framework for understanding how humans are using signs, symbols and icons to make a meaning around them, an important assumption of semiotics is that signs don't convey a meaning that is inherent to the object being represented. Scholars of modern linguistics understand that words do not have innate meanings but the word, sounds or letters are related to that particular object which convey the meaning.

The mystery authors developed the ability to dispense the meaning with words and humans are able to describe the abstract meaning. This means humans have words for things that may not be able to actually see in front of us. For Saussure, language itself makes the meaning rather than

carrying meaning. Therefore, our experience is always influenced by the language which people use to describe it. When authors understand that language is a sign system and not just a naming of objects, mystery authors are able to analyze the various meanings entrenched in the novels and how signs influence meanings.

2.2. THE DA VINCI CODE AND ANGELS AND DEMONS, NOVELS – A MYSTERY AND SEMIOTIC ANALYSIS

The Da Vinci Code is a mystery-detective novel by Dan Brown which published in 2003. The novel sold over 80 million copies worldwide and became best seller novel in the year 2009. It translated into 44 different languages. This novel furnished fame and popularity to the author Dan Brown. This is the wonderful novel with the pack of several signs, symbols which promotes to the readers to decode it and semiotic study made it easy. This is a best seller novel gaining the top place in the *New York Times Best Seller list* during its first week of release in 2003. The author Dan Brown has created the following element of mysteries and researcher try to analyse semiotic expression in *The Da Vinci Code*. The signifier of Priory of Sion and its signified meaning is portrait in many layers in Dan Brown 's 2003's novel, *The Da Vinci Code* becomes world's bestselling novel in the same year 2003. After the publication of this novel people took interest in priory of Sion, the symbolic image of Priory of Sion reveals the several truths of the secret society. The Priory of Sion is a group of secret society that has a reason to conspiracy theories. However, it is difficult to authenticity Dan Brown indorses the mythical claims side of the priory of Sion, Brown Writes about the facts of The Priory of Sion 'at the beginning of the novel on Fact page, lead him to the next clue and here Brown writes that Leonardo Da Vinci was also the grandmaster of Priory. Mystery starts from here to the last of the novel and it reveals to the end of the novel. *New York Times* hails the novel to be,

“Wow Blockbuster perfection an exhilaratingly brainy thriller. Not since the advent of Harry Potter has an author so flagrantly delighted in leading readers on a breathless chase.”

(The Da Vinci Code Acclaim from Around the World)

The present novel follows symbologist Robert Langdon, he is the protagonist of the novel and the very symbologist of Harvard University. He is very excellent man who discovers many coded messages, signs, symbols with its logical solution and finds actual place of Holy Grail and second protagonist is Sophie Neveu, a French cryptologist. She is the granddaughter of Jacques Sauniere, a museum 's curator. She works for the department of cryptology, as they investigate a murder mystery in Paris 's Louvre Museum. It also discovers a battle between two secret societies, Priory of Sion and Opus Dei and focus on the secret of Holy Grail. This novel determines the relationship between Mary Magdalene and Jesus they having been married or not. Robert Langdon was found the murder victim in Grand Gallery of Louvre Museum at the very beginning of the novel and mystery starts from here till the end of the novel.

2.2.1. The Priory of Sion

Fig. 1 <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Priory_of_Sion>

The signifier of Priory of Sion and its signified meaning is portrait in many layers in Dan Brown 's 2003's novel, *The Da Vinci Code* becomes world's bestselling novel in the same year 2003. After the publication of this novel people took interest in priory of Sion, the symbolic image

of Priory of Sion reveals the several truths of the secret society. The Priory of Sion is a group of secret society that has a reason to conspiracy theories. However, it is difficult to authenticity Dan Brown indorses the mythical claims side of the priory of Sion, Brown Writes about the facts of The Priory of Sion 'at the beginning of the novel on Fact page, lead him to the next clue and here Brown writes that Leonardo Da Vinci was also the grandmaster of Priory. Mystery starts from here to the last of the novel and it reveals to the end of the novel.

2.2.2. Fibonacci Sequence-

In this novel a Fibonacci sequence plays a direct role in the storyline and in the plot as a coded message left by the murder victim. The Fibonacci sequence was written by murder victim and this was a great clue to find out the mystery behind the murder of museum's curator. He wrote this message in following words and numbers;

“13-3-2-21-1-1-8-5

O, Draconian devil!

Oh, lame saint!” (*The Da Vinci Code Page No.65*)

The numbers are,

“13-3-2-21-1-1-8-5”

In this sequence they are arranged in out of order, this clue directs the investigator or protagonist, Robert Langdon to find out the murder mystery. The actual sequence is, “1-1-2-3-5-8-13-21” Means the two numbers when we add with each other the next number will come, this is very important first clue which helps to solve the murder mystery of Jacques Sauniere, the novel's use of the ancient number sequence created by 13th century mathematician Fibonacci. He

suggested in which all life grows in a common progression, with each number equaling the sum of the preceding once. As per the plot of this novel The Fibonacci sequence is the first clue of this mysterious murder, when the protagonist arranged these words in correct order, he got some meaningful words,

O, Draconian Devil!

Oh, lame saint!

The perfect anagrams of these words are,

Leonardo da Vinci!

The Mona Lisa!

2.2.3. Vitruvian Man

Fig. 2. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/file:Da_Vinci_Vitruve

The Vitruvian Man is a Leonardo da Vinci's most famous drawing based upon the work of ancient Roman architect Vitruvius who was a proponent of using human proportion in building. Vitruvian Man is the most important clue in this novel's opening scene. The museum's curator Jacques Sauniere draws one pentacle on his body; he posed like the Vitruvian Man with cryptic message written beside his body. This position leads protagonist Robert Langdon near to

the Leonardo da Vinci's drawings. Here this drawing has been creating some suspense and wants some clearance about it. Ancient Roman architect Vitruvius described his idea in Book III of his treaties *De Architectura*. This drawing is based upon human proportion. With some geometric descriptions and it exemplifies the blend of art and science. During the Renaissance and it shows Leonardo's keen interest in proportion the text has two parts, it was made as a study of the proportion of the male human body as described by him. This image has been used for various symbolic purposes and for Fictional and non-Fictional media. This image also used for NASA; Vitruvian Man appears on a patch worn on the right shoulder of the American Extravehicular Mobility Unit (EMU). This image is used as the stylized figures of Vitruvian Man have been adopted for the icons which representing accessibility in Mac OS and Gnome desktop

3.1. Element of Mystery and Semiotic Signs in *Angels and Demons*.

3.1.1. Illuminati

Fig.3. Adam Weishaupt (1748–1830), founder of the Bavarian Illuminati.
<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Angels_%26_Demons>

Illuminati is the name of secret society which was founded in May 1, 1776. It works to oppose superstition, prejudice, and religious influence over public life and to support gender equality and women's education. The main goal of this organization was to eliminate superstition and religious influence over the government, philosophy and science. The group has also been

called the Bavarian Illuminati and its ideology has been called Illuminism. In this novel author Dan Brown brings this ancient secret society, named Illuminati. Mystery starts from here to the end of the novel. Here researcher unveils the mystery and several semiotic signs and reveals the meaning of the behind this particular society. In present novel Leonardo Vitra, a scientist is murdered and his chest is branded with an ambigram of the word Illuminati. Kohler contacts Robert Langdon; he is an expert on the Illuminati, who determines the ambigram is authentic. This secret society has stolen the antimatter and tried to destroy the Vatican City. Robert Langdon and Vittoria Vetra these two protagonists' effort to save the Vatican City. The Illuminati has played a great role in this novel. This novel revolves around the secrets of Illuminati.

3.3.2. Path of Illumination- Four Clues in Angels and Demons

Dan Brown presents the Illuminati a secret society had a secret path. The Path of Illumination, the protagonist Robert Langdon and Vittoria Vetra attempts to retrace the Path of Illumination, and they follow a series of clues left in various famous landmarks in and around Rome. The four cardinals are missing-kidnapped from their Vatican rooms-before the Conclave begins. Langdon has another task that he has find the antimatter which has been stolen from a CERN laboratory.

- 1. Bernini's *Habbakuk and the Angel*, and Agostino Chigi's pyramidal wall tomb**
- 2. West Ponente at Saint Peter's Square**
- 3. Ecstasy of St Teresa**
- 4. The Fountain of Four Rivers**

Each sculpture had a symbolic and its semiotic meaning of science's four altars. The book is a suspense novel and grabs the attention of the readers on the history of Christianity and Illuminati. The ambigrams of Illuminati and the four elements of science along with the Illuminati

diamond makes the story even more jaw dropping. This story is actually a blend of science and religion and fiction and facts. The writing is simple and clear, therefore making it easier for the reader to keep pace with the fast-paced plot. The murders are occurred in various places and killer gives challenge to Langdon. Robert Langdon is successful to find out the murder places but never successes in to save the cardinals. In this novel the element of mystery is unsealed by the researcher with the four altars of science.

The Illuminati Pyramid has four clues,

‘The symbol of Illuminati was a pyramid with the emblem of the all-seeing-eye-inside-a symbol you can see today on the dollar bill. The four-sided pyramid represents the four mystic elements of the Illuminati Earth, Air, Fire, and Water. The triangular shaped walls of the pyramid replicate the Greek symbol deita which means change. Lastly all seeing-eye was symbol of the Illuminati’s Omniscient presence in European society.’

(Angels and Demons official Tour the Path of Illumination)

Killer used four elements of science Earth, Air, Fire and Water. Each cardinal was branded with these elements, first branded with Earth ambigram and had soil forced in his mouth. Second branded with Air and his lungs punctured. Third cardinal with Fire and was burned alive. The last cardinal branded with Water and was left to drown at the bottom of a fountain. - In this novel frequently uses Latin phrases and emphasizing the mystery of ancient knowledge and secret societies. Many codes and puzzles functioning as narrative devices. The cross and Catholic churches, imageries made the conflict between faith and reason. The Papal Conclave is not just a

political event but it symbolizes the ritualistic and nature of the church. The story follows a journey of the hero who uncover the hidden truth.

CONCLUSION

People enjoy the semiotic signs and the mystery story because there is reason behind it that they are try to figure out the answer to a puzzle. When we compare this fiction with other fiction, we find this fiction which had profound secrets in which sometimes it wholly unknown. It gives a challenge to human mind because it is beyond the human comprehension. There is some overlap with thriller and suspense novels. Mystery hangs you till the end of the novel. After studying and analyzing these novels the researcher came across the following conclusion. Mysterious semiotic signs create wonder in reader's mind. Many symbols, clues are revealed by protagonist and author does not present the whole story and his idea in front of readers. So that readers try to fill these gaps according to his knowledge and connecting the information which is presented by author. Even in Hollywood and Bollywood films are also based on this interesting element. Many films become very popular and earned lots of earnings and fame. Dan Brown's three novels are transformed into films. In both the novels researcher has observed some similarities like, both the novels begin with an act of murder of a significant person. In *The Da Vinci Code* a museum's curator, Jacques Sauniere murdered by a monk of Opus Dei and in *Angles and Demons* a scientist Leonardo Vetra is also murdered by an Assassin. These two novels contain breath taking mystery stories. Even in Hollywood and Bollywood films are also based on this interesting element. Many films become very popular and earned lots of earnings and fame. Dan Brown's three novels are transformed into films. *The Da Vinci Code*, *Angles and Demons* and *The Lost Symbol*, Brown used his knowledge and writing skill for develop the story line and his symbols, historical societies, character, and icons are made the novel pulse-quickenning; Mysterious semiotic signs create

wonder in reader's mind. Many symbols, clues are revealed by protagonist and author does not present the whole story and his idea in front of readers. So that readers try to fill these gaps according to his knowledge and connecting the information which is presented by author. An attempt has been made to focus and highlight some semiotic analysis of these two novels.

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